

**MANAGEMENT PRACTICES IN MULTIPROFESSIONAL RESIDENCE IN
HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT**

PROBLEMATIZANDO LAS PRÁCTICAS DE GESTIÓN CLÍNICA EN LA RESIDENCIA
MULTIPROFESIONAL EN GESTIÓN HOSPITALARIA

PROBLEMATIZANDO PRÁTICAS DE GESTÃO DA CLÍNICA NA RESIDÊNCIA
MULTIPROFISSIONAL EM GESTÃO HOSPITALAR

Bárbara Estevam Ferreira Santana ¹

Marco Aurelio Bertúlio das Neves ²

Mara Regina Rosa Ribeiro ³

Rosanna Iozzi Silva ⁴

Gímerson Erick Ferreira ⁵

Manuscript submitted in: December 21, 2024.

Approved in: June 23, 2025.

Published in: August 11, 2025.

Abstract

In the context of training for health services management, multidisciplinary residencies in hospital management represent a strategic differential for the implementation of principles and guidelines of the Unified Health System (SUS). This article aimed to investigate clinical management practices undertaken in a multidisciplinary residency program in hospital management. This is an applied, descriptive, qualitative research methodologically based on the problematization proposed by the Maguerez Arch. The data were analyzed through thematic content analysis. The results highlight both potentializing and limiting elements of the residency in hospital management, in addition to indicating solutions for practical teaching within the perspective of the residency program, based on the experiences lived by residents in problem situations. It is concluded that the standardization of educational processes in the residency constitutes a strategy to strengthen the autonomy of the actors involved and contributes to the implementation of principles for clinical management, promoting a greater connection between teaching and the reality of the professional field.

¹ Master's degree in Public Health from the Federal University of Mato Grosso. Employee at the Municipal Health Department of Cuiabá.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6687-4139> Contact: estevam.barbara@gmail.com

² Doctorate student in Public Health and Master's degree in Health and Environment from the Federal University of Mato Grosso. Professor at the Federal University of Mato Grosso and Technician at the Mato Grosso State Health Department.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0685-9233> Contact: marcobertulio@marcobertulio.com

³ Doctorate in Nursing from the University of São Paulo. Professor in the Postgraduate Program in Nursing at the Federal University of Mato Grosso. Leader of the Research Group on Management, Education, and Training in Health and Nursing.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7132-3005> Contact: mrrribeiro@gmail.com

⁴ Doctorate in Public Health from the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro. Retired physician from the Rio de Janeiro Municipal Health Department.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0127-4324> Contact: rosannaiozzi@yahoo.com.br

⁵ Doctorate in Nursing from the Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul. Professor in the Graduate Program in Sciences Applied to Hospital Care and in the Graduate Program in Nursing at the Federal University of Mato Grosso.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4039-0205> Contact: gimersonerick@gmail.com

Keywords: Internship and residency; Education, graduate; Problem-based learning; Clinical governance; Interprofessional education.

Resumen

En el contexto de la formación para la gestión de servicios de salud, las residencias multidisciplinares en gestión hospitalaria representan un diferenciador estratégico para la implementación de principios y directrices del Sistema Único de Salud (SUS). Este artículo tuvo como objetivo investigar las prácticas de gestión clínica realizadas en un programa de residencia multidisciplinario en gestión hospitalaria. Se trata de una investigación aplicada, descriptiva, cualitativa, basada metodológicamente en la problematización propuesta por Arco de Maguerez. Los datos fueron analizados mediante análisis de contenido temático. Los resultados resaltan elementos potenciadores y limitantes de la residencia en la gestión hospitalaria, además de indicar soluciones para la enseñanza práctica en la perspectiva del programa de residencia, a partir de las experiencias vividas por los residentes en situaciones problemáticas. Se concluye que la estandarización de los procesos educativos en residencia constituye una estrategia para fortalecer la autonomía de los actores involucrados y contribuye a la implementación de principios para la gestión clínica, promoviendo una relación más estrecha entre la docencia y la realidad del campo profesional.

Palabras clave: Internato y residencia; Educación de postgrado; Aprendizaje basado en problemas; Gestión clínica; Educación interprofesional.

Resumo

No contexto da formação para a gestão de serviços de saúde, as residências multiprofissionais em gestão hospitalar representam um diferencial estratégico para a implementação de princípios e diretrizes do Sistema Único de Saúde (SUS). O presente artigo teve como objetivo investigar práticas de gestão da clínica empreendidas em um programa de residência multiprofissional em gestão hospitalar. Trata-se de pesquisa aplicada, descritiva, qualitativa, fundamentada metodologicamente na problematização proposta pelo Arco de Maguerez. Os dados foram analisados por meio da análise de conteúdo temática. Os resultados evidenciam tanto elementos potencializadores quanto limitantes da residência em gestão hospitalar, além de indicar soluções para o ensino prático dentro da perspectiva do programa de residência, com base nas experiências vivenciadas pelos residentes em situações-problema. Conclui-se que a uniformização dos processos educacionais na residência constitui uma estratégia para fortalecer a autonomia dos atores envolvidos e contribui para a implementação de princípios para a gestão da clínica, promovendo uma maior aproximação entre o ensino e a realidade do campo profissional.

Palavras-chave: Residência hospitalar; Educação de pós-graduação; Aprendizagem baseada em problemas; Gestão clínica; Educação interprofissional.

Introduction

In the contemporary scenario, educational initiatives at the postgraduate level, especially in residency programs, have been developed with the aim of promoting policies and actions for continuing education in health. These programs aim to train professionals to perform differently in the Unified Health System (SUS), with an emphasis on interdisciplinary construction, teamwork, and the reorientation of techno-assistance practices (Carneiro; Teixeira; Pedrosa, 2021).

Created with the enactment of Law n.º 11.129, of 2005, multiprofessional health residencies (MHR) are guided by SUS principles and guidelines, considering local and regional needs and realities, and covering various health professions (Brazil, 2006). In this sense, they constitute spaces conducive to interprofessional education, stimulating integration between professionals from different areas and seeking permanent qualification, which is a widely disseminated ethical commitment in health organizations (Casanova; Batista; Moreno, 2018; Carneiro; Teixeira; Pedrosa, 2021).

Among the various types of multiprofessional residencies, those focused on management stand out, with proposals for training professionals to work in the management of health organizations, services, and processes at various points in the healthcare network (RAS). The focus of management residencies is to bring health professionals closer to the administration of health services and processes, a proposal that is still under-explored in undergraduate courses in the field (Oliveira; Cavalcante; Pinto, 2023).

In this context, clinical management emerges as a relevant approach, as it is structured around complementary axes that seek to articulate health care, management, and education practices. Initially proposed in Brazil by Eugênio Vilaça Mendes (2001), clinical management incorporates elements of clinical governance and managed care, such as risk management, clinical auditing, clinical effectiveness, education and training, people management, patient/public involvement, and use of information. It is a set of micro-management technologies that, based on evidence and clinical guidelines, aims to provide humane, equitable, timely, safe, efficient, effective, and quality care that is people-centered, shared, and guided by best performance standards (Padilha et al., 2018; Mendes, 2019).

The operationalization of clinic management requires a problem-solving approach, focusing on the production of transformative interventions guided by people's health needs and the coordination and sharing of knowledge and decisions among the different actors involved in providing comprehensive, quality, and safe care (Padilha et al., 2018). Its principles are based on practices that promote an environment of excellence, safety, quality, and focus on the needs of individuals, as well as the continuous improvement of services (Padilha et al., 2018; Mendes, 2019).

Considering the potential of this approach, many Brazilian university hospitals, currently managed by the Brazilian Hospital Services Company (EBSERH) (Abbade, 2022), have implemented principles for clinical management in the implementation of their organizational model, with the aim of improving clinical processes and boosting the development of organizations and health systems (Vieira, 2016; Abbade, 2022). However, the implementation of such principles still represents a challenge, as it requires strategic alignment between continuing health education actions, organizational process management, and the health care provided.

Thus, multiprofessional residencies should promote critical reflection on work and training processes, facilitating the identification of everyday problems and the development of strategies to solve them, based on the experiences of residents (Flor et al., 2023). Fostering reflective dialogue between clinical management practices and the reality of work provides an opportunity to understand practices as subject to review, adopting a problematizing learning perspective that favors innovation in health care products and processes (Padilha et al., 2018). Consequently, transformations are promoted in multiprofessional and educational practices and in the organization of work, favoring integration between training, management, care, and social participation (Carneiro; Teixeira; Pedrosa, 2021).

Therefore, considering that one of the major challenges to the effectiveness of the SUS in the current scenario is related to management, problematizing hospital management training processes is important and necessary to meet the demands of health work and to disseminate the knowledge necessary for scientific and technological advancement. In this context, problematizing practices in light of clinical management proves to be an even more proactive strategy, considering the principles for its implementation, which aim to transform practices through the articulation between health care, management, and education.

Given this, the following question arises: Which clinical management practices, undertaken within the scope of a multiprofessional residency program in hospital management, can be problematized with a view to improving training? To this end, the study aimed to problematize the clinical management practices undertaken in a multiprofessional residency program in hospital management.

Literature review

The increase in the age pyramid in the older age groups and the decline in birth rates have had a direct impact on the costs of maintaining the quality of life and longevity of this population. This scenario highlights the complexity of dealing with chronic diseases and organizing healthcare practices in an integrated and organized manner (Mendes, 2019). It is essential to ensure service quality in an integrated and complex system such as the SUS, which, in turn, poses challenges for its creation and operation. In this context, the RAS-based model becomes necessary, requiring new management strategies. Clinical management emerges as an innovative solution to address these challenges (Barros et al., 2020).

According to Acioli (2012), clinical management seeks, among other objectives, to reduce the costs of services and procedures while maintaining quality and ensuring a fair and balanced remuneration system. The model is linked to the decentralization of responsibilities and the improvement of the relationship between professionals, management, and users, considering the costs involved (Barros et al., 2020). The structuring of care under its principles must meet the real needs of the population, in a co-responsible manner, with a focus on quality standards, and promote collaboration between knowledge, practices, and continuous educational actions, involving the various social actors and points of care (Schmitz et al., 2021).

In light of the National Hospital Care Policy (PNHOSP), clinic management emerges as a set of care, management, and educational practices aligned with user demands. This involves bed management, team co-responsibility, and the evaluation of care indicators. Bed management, for example, seeks to optimize utilization, increasing turnover within technical criteria and reducing unnecessary hospitalizations. Therefore, the horizontalization of care organizes work in a continuous and integrated manner, with multiprofessional reference teams (Mendes, 2019). In this way, the implementation of expanded clinical care and clinical management, with multidisciplinary teams, strengthens the bond between staff, users, and family members, taking into account subjective and social aspects. This model also ensures the presence of a companion and open visits, in accordance with PNHOSP guidelines (Santos; Pinto, 2017).

Padilha *et al.* (2018) highlights the triad of health care, management, and education, initially proposed by Mendes (2011), as essential to ensuring the centrality of the comprehensive health care model, with quality and safety, oriented to the needs of the individual and the collective. Therefore, mobilization for clinical management, with the understanding and application of its principles, promotes a culture that values quality, safety, co-responsibility, transparency, and comprehensive care. These initiatives contribute to the improvement of healthcare processes, transforming care, management, and education practices (Schmitz *et al.*, 2021).

In this context, it is important to consider the institutionalization of new management models, such as MHR. These, defined as full-time, postgraduate programs under the supervision of faculty and healthcare professionals, have shared responsibility between education, healthcare, and healthcare management, integrating teaching, service, and community, and promoting transformations to reorient the practices of the hegemonic model (Flor *et al.*, 2023).

Methods

The research followed a qualitative and descriptive approach, conducted between September 2019 and April 2020, at a university hospital (UH) in the federal public health network in the Midwest of Brazil, managed by the EBSERH network and linked to a federal public university. The study focused on the multiprofessional residency program in hospital management for the SUS, one of two programs operating at the hospital, thus delimiting the scope of the investigation.

According to the National Register of Health Establishments (CNES), the HU has 1,139 employees, is classified as a general hospital, and offers eight surgical specialties, four complementary specialties, seven clinical specialties, and three obstetric/pediatric specialties, in addition to 108 beds. The HU has an education and research management department in its organizational chart that is responsible for monitoring residency programs and provides infrastructure consisting of classrooms, meeting rooms, videoconferencing rooms, an auditorium, a computer room, a clinical research laboratory, a library, access to databases, and a health simulation center.

With regard to multiprofessional residency, 21 places are offered, 15 of which are in the area of adult and elderly health, with an emphasis on cardiovascular care, aimed at professionals in nursing, social work, nutrition, and psychology. The other six places are for the hospital management program for the SUS focused on in this study, which was implemented in 2015. This program is aimed at professionals in public health, nursing, pharmacy, and nutrition, and lasts two years (Brazil, 2022).

The program has 11 tutors and 33 preceptors distributed across different areas of management, such as administrative management, hospitalization management, outpatient management, health care management, diagnostic and therapeutic support, teaching and research management, health regulation and evaluation management, information technology management, and quality.

From an ethical standpoint, the research is part of the matrix research project “Artifacts for the implementation of clinical management in a university hospital.” The hospital's Research Ethics Committee, in accordance with CNS Resolution 466/2012 and Operational Standard No. 001/2013 of the National Health Council, approved the project under opinion No. 3,285,978, with CAAE registration: 09495919.9.0000.5541 on the Brazil Platform. The study received support from the hospital's teaching and research management, which authorized data collection, and was approved by the institution's human resources department. Thus, the research was incorporated into the organizational dynamics through an integrated institutional training project, including the Free and Informed Consent Form for the application of an online questionnaire.

Thirty-five professionals linked to the residency program participated in the study, including residents in the areas of Public Health, Nursing, Nutrition, and Pharmacy, as well as educational managers, tutors, preceptors, and teachers. The inclusion criteria were professionals who had been linked to the program for at least three months. Those who were absent during data collection were excluded. The workshops were formally recorded and certified, and participants were invited in person at their workplaces, where the research objectives were explained. After accepting, participants registered via a link that detailed the activities and contained the consent form.

The methodology adopted was the Problematization Methodology (PM), an active educational approach that intentionally works with the problematization of contexts. Through the participation of those involved and the valorization of their prior knowledge and experiences, PM seeks to uncover explanatory factors and stimulate the proposal of solutions based on scientific knowledge. Based on the Philosophy of Praxis by Adolfo Sánchez Vásquez and the Problematizing Pedagogy by Paulo Freire, PM proposes the construction of knowledge through action on reality, which occurs through reflection and guides the subject in transformation through praxis (Marin et al., 2010). Therefore, the study was anchored in the theoretical-methodological proposal of Arco de Magueréz (Figure 1), which starts from lived reality as a starting point and consists of five phases: observation of reality, identification of key points, theorization, formulation of solution hypotheses, and application of these solutions to reality. The last phase involves returning to reality with the aim of transforming it (Berbel; Gamboa, 2011).

Figure 1 – Stages of the Magueréz Arc used by Berbel.

Source: Prepared by the authors.

Data was produced through problem-solving workshops, with five face-to-face meetings and one virtual activity, totaling 21 hours. The workshops followed the Magueréz Arc phases and used methodologies adaptable to organizational quality systems, such as the Explanatory Problem Network, to identify issues in a structured manner. Tools such as 5W2H, Ishikawa Diagram, and brainstorming were applied to design solutions and identify causes and effects of problems. The Problem Analysis and

Solution Methodology (MASP) was used to optimize processes, with the help of an external consultant who facilitated the analysis and discussion of the residency program's problems. To facilitate the problem identification process and group discussions, an external consultant gave a presentation explaining the tool and the MASP, acting as a facilitator and impartially assisting participants in analyzing the problems. Figure 2 illustrates the workshops planned for applying the Maguerez Arc.

Figure 2 – Summary flowchart with the research and workshop planning stages.

Source: Prepared by the authors, based on the hospital's training project, 2020.

Initially, six face-to-face sessions were scheduled, but workshops 5 and 6 were held together due to issues with participants' availability. The first session consisted of an exercise to align expectations, called the “expectation tree,” followed by a presentation on the creation, objectives, and rules of the residency program, as well as a lecture on the skills of preceptors and tutors. At the end, participants were asked to complete a dispersal activity sent by email. On the second day of the workshop, a brainstorming session was held to learn about the perspectives of those involved. Considering the intense hospital dynamics and the need to obtain as many responses as possible, it was decided to conduct the brainstorming online. Each participant received a link to fill out a form with questions about the program, in order to identify the problems experienced by tutors, preceptors, and residents. The form, consisting of eight topics with open-ended questions, aimed to have participants describe, based on their perceptions, the problems faced in the program.

In the second stage, Key Points, the responses to the online form were analyzed using thematic content analysis, as proposed by Minayo (2001), following the stages of pre-analysis, exploration of the material, and treatment of the results and interpretation. The presentation of this compilation guided the next stage, in which participants discussed and explained the problems.

During the Theorization stage, the groups were divided to analyze the problems from different perspectives (tutors/preceptors and residents). The Ishikawa Diagram was used to identify the real causes of the problems, and the perceptions of each group were analyzed separately. During the Solution Hypotheses stage, the MASP, Ishikawa Diagram, and 5W2H tools were used to define the causes of the problems and develop an action plan. The solutions were applied throughout the workshops, with the aim of implementing the methodologies in a practical way, encouraging the transformation of the reality experienced and ensuring integration with the real context.

Results and discussion

The results are presented according to the five stages developed, focusing on the problematization of clinical management practices in the multiprofessional residency program in hospital management. The findings at each stage will be

presented, detailing how the methodologies and tools applied helped to identify and analyze the challenges faced by the participants. Table 1 summarizes the application of the MP, serving as a basis for subsequent discussions in the hospital management scenario.

Table 1 – Application of the Maguerez Arc in problematizing practices in the program.

MOMENTS FROM THE MAGUEREZ ARC	ACTIVITIES UNDERTAKEN
1. Observation of reality	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Survey of participants' expectations; 2. Presentation of the history of the residency program and its practices; 3. Presentation of the definitions and duties of tutors and preceptors; 4. Brainstorming to identify problems faced; 5. Preliminary analysis of responses and compilation of the most frequently mentioned problems
2. Key points	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Presentation and discussion of compiled responses; 2. Identification of the most relevant problems and their prioritization; 3. Formation of discussion groups; 4. Application of tools for detailed analysis of problems; 5. Presentation of each group's results after completion.
3. Theorization	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. General discussion about the problems identified and their causes; 2. (Re)analysis of the brainstorming session, incorporating the perspectives of tutors, preceptors, and residents; 3. Definition of the underlying problem, focusing on the most critical aspects that affect clinical management practices in the residency program.
4. Hypotheses for solutions	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Application of the Ishikawa diagram to analyze the causes and effects related to the problems identified; 2. Use of the 5W2H tool to detail the actions needed to solve the problems; 3. Formulation of hypotheses for solutions based on the tools applied.
5. Application to reality	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Team meetings in the sectors involved to discuss solutions; 2. Integration of the new residency class into the program; 3. Structuring of essential documents for the organization and planning of the residency (class schedule, internal regulations, evaluation forms for tutors, preceptors, and residents, and rotation schedule for the sectors).

Source: Prepared by the authors.

- Moment 1: Observation of Reality

The Reality Observation moment began with the Expectations Tree exercise, a playful activity that reflected the participants' previous experiences in the context of the multiprofessional residency. At this point, participants shared their expectations regarding mentoring, learning, and management. The most frequently mentioned expectations involved knowledge, interaction, communication, organization, process improvement, planning, results, assignments, working with residents, identifying gaps, and standardization.

These statements indicated a desire for a collaborative environment focused on knowledge exchange and continuous improvement. Tutors/preceptors sought to improve their teaching practices and learn more about teaching strategies, while residents highlighted the need to organize and optimize the field of practice, with a clear definition of responsibilities. The multiprofessional residency, therefore, is a challenging but essential space for the development of integrated and humanized interprofessional work, in line with the collaborative teaching proposal.

Recent scientific literature corroborates these findings by highlighting that multiprofessional health residency is a model that favors a more integrated and collaborative approach to professional formation. According to Nunes, Mângia, and Lima (2020), the teaching process in multiprofessional residency allows for the joint construction of knowledge, valuing the contributions of each area of health and favoring a more holistic and interprofessional learning experience. In addition, communication, collaboration, and interaction among participants are key aspects of this process (Rodrigues; Witt, 2022), aligning with the expectations identified in this study. The interactions between preceptors and residents are highlighted in the study by Sousa, Falbo-Neto, and Falbo (2021) as fruitful, as they demonstrate learning, updating, and planning, resulting from the creation of a good environment for interaction, the adjustment of the tutor to the level of the residents, and the encouragement of discussions.

During the brainstorming session, 24 participants (10 residents and 14 tutors/preceptors) contributed to raising awareness of everyday perceptions and problems in the residency. The analysis revealed recurring themes and critical areas that needed attention, deepening understanding of the difficulties faced by participants and reinforcing the importance of a more integrated learning environment.

The study identified that, despite the residency being an intense learning environment, it faces challenges in organizing the field of practice and defining responsibilities. These aspects can impact the quality of formation and the construction of interprofessionality, reflecting the principles of clinical management, which advocates the organization and coordination of work processes for quality, safe, and patient-centered health care (Mendes, 2019). In this sense, clinical management is an important strategy for organizing the practice field and promoting continuous improvement in teaching processes.

The findings indicate the need for more structured and integrated management in the residency program. The performance of tutors/preceptors and residents should be better coordinated to ensure that activities meet the needs of formation and improvement of work processes. Strengthening communication, planning, and organization of the field of practice is essential to make the residency a more effective space for collaborative learning, as recommended by clinical management (Mendes, 2019).

Furthermore, reflection on the results reveals that, although participants' expectations show a willingness for change and improvement, it is essential that the educational process in the residences be constantly reevaluated and adjusted so that the gaps observed can be adequately filled. It is also necessary to consider that organizational difficulties and unclear responsibilities can lead to frustration among participants, which can compromise the effectiveness of the teaching process. Therefore, it is essential that the management of the residency be guided by principles of collectivity, flexibility, and dialogue, always with the aim of promoting a learning environment that values the contributions of all professionals involved, as indicated in the literature (Oliveira; Cavalcante; Pinto, 2023; Silva et al., 2023).

The findings reinforce the importance of multiprofessional residency as an innovative teaching model that requires constant attention to the management of its internal processes. For the residency to fulfill its role of integrated and humanized formation, it is crucial that all those involved work collaboratively and that organizational issues are resolved effectively, in line with the principles of clinical management. This initial diagnosis led to the transition to the second stage of the MP, focused on analyzing key points and seeking interprofessional and collaborative solutions.

- Moment 2: Key points

Participants analyzed the results of the Expectation Tree exercise and the compilation of the brainstorming session, identifying issues that emerged from the previous stage. The main topics addressed were: lack of definition of the competencies of preceptors and tutors, absence of knowledge premises in the sectors for residents, lack of definition of essential sectors for formation, and inadequate planning of

rotations. In addition, challenges such as insufficient physical space/equipment, lack of involvement of preceptors in the operationalization of the residency, poor communication among those involved, and lack of support for residents, especially in relation to structure and support services, were highlighted.

These points reflect structural and organizational difficulties in the multiprofessional residency environment, which, despite being a collaborative and integrative space, faces challenges in its implementation. The literature indicates that a clear definition of the competencies of those involved and the efficient organization of spaces are essential for the success of multiprofessional residency (Sousa; Falbo-Neto; Falbo, 2021; Rodrigues; Witt, 2022). The lack of planning and communication between coordinators, tutors, and residents is also frequently cited as an obstacle to the effectiveness of interprofessional practices (Oliveira; Cavalcante; Pinto, 2023; Gomes et al., 2023).

Participants were divided into groups to discuss the relevance and governability of the identified themes, using the Explanatory Problem Network and 5W2H tools. Each group chose the tool with which it felt most comfortable and reflected on the determining factors for improving processes, proposing solutions applicable to their daily lives. Proposed work plans were presented and discussed collectively, refining ideas and planning concrete actions. The main topics that emerged were: defining competencies for preceptors and tutors; the knowledge and practice requirements for residents in each sector; the definition of essential sectors for resident formation; efficient planning of rotations; insufficient physical space/equipment; the inclusion of preceptors in the residency operationalization process; resident support; standardization of the work plan; and communication among those involved.

These points reflect the main challenges faced by the residency program to improve its effectiveness. The analysis and discussion, aligned with the principles of clinical management, allowed us to identify key factors for the program's advancement, promoting a reflective dialogue between management and practice and stimulating critical reflection on the challenges of the residency program and the engagement of different actors in the search for solutions.

The application of these tools highlights the importance of management in the organization of educational processes in the MHR, a field that, although challenging, offers great opportunities for collaborative, interprofessional, and holistic learning, as

highlighted by Gomes et al. (2023). The groups' proposals aim to systematize practices, improve communication, and optimize the organization of the field of practice, aligning with clinical management guidelines, which should promote articulation between learning and practice for collaborative and integrated results (Mendes, 2019; Silva et al., 2023).

The results indicate that, although residency is recognized as an innovative model, there are organizational and structural barriers to overcome to ensure its effectiveness. Improving the definition of competencies, the planning of rotations, and communication among those involved are aspects that can make residency more integrative and humanized. Residency management needs to be more structured and continuously reviewed, taking into account feedback from participants and the specificities of each work context, with a view to interprofessional and collaborative learning.

- Moment 3: Thorization

In the third stage of the Maguerz Arc, called Theoretical Framework, participants were reorganized into two groups, with guidance from an external consultant, to ensure effective use of the management tools. Before beginning to apply the tools, an explanation of their concept and use was provided to avoid confusion between causes and structural problems. The focus was on reflecting on the issues raised in the previous phase, considering the perspectives of students (Group 1) and tutors/preceptors (Group 2). Group 1 highlighted deficiencies that compromise the program's effectiveness, such as the lack of continuous evaluation of residents, the absence of a program identity, the lack of definition of the workload and duties of tutors and preceptors, and the lack of collective commitment. Group 2 indicated issues such as lack of management support, definition of the resident's competency profile, lack of training for tutors, and the need to restructure the pedagogical project.

These findings confirm that, although the multiprofessional residency is designed to be holistic and collaborative, it faces structural challenges. The literature also indicates a lack of clarity in the evaluation processes and in the definition of the competency profile of residents as recurring problems, which compromises the

formation of residents and the effectiveness of the multiprofessional model (Rodrigues; Witt, 2022; Oliveira; Cavalcante; Pinto, 2023).

The use of fishbone tools and analysis forms allowed the groups to reflect on the causes of these deficiencies, defining the structural problem. The application of these principles to clinical management was evident, considering the sociocultural, individual, and institutional contexts in the construction of knowledge (Padilha et al., 2018). This approach guided a critical reflection on the causes and effects of failures in the formation process, taking into account the local realities and expectations of those involved. After analysis, the groups identified two main structural problems: the lack of structure of the residency program and the non-institutionalization of the program, reflecting a gap between governance and the actors involved in the residency. This mismatch directly impacts the training and identity of residents, compromising the effectiveness of training and the quality of services provided.

Therefore, the central problem identified was the ineffectiveness of resident training in hospital management, resulting from a lack of integration between management, tutors, residents, and the pedagogical project. With the problem defined, a design was presented that served as a graphical representation of the stages and workflows, helping to identify flaws and areas for improvement in the resident training process (Figure 3).

Clinical management, as highlighted by Mendes (2019), is directly linked to the organization of educational processes. In the context of multiprofessional residency, ineffective training is not only a pedagogical failure, but also a management failure. Management must be dynamic, adjusting educational practices according to the needs of residents and the community. Therefore, the analysis of key points, such as the lack of standardization and clarity in the competencies of tutors, highlights the need for more structured management with integrated strategic planning.

In addition, interprofessional training requires management that integrates knowledge and practices, which is not yet fully implemented in the program investigated. The residency model is still far from a fully collaborative process, negatively impacting learning and the applicability of the skills acquired. Therefore, process management should be seen as essential to creating an integrated and humanized learning environment, aligned with the demands of holistic and interprofessional health care (Nunes; Mângia; Lima, 2020).

Figure 3 – Resident formation process.

Source: Prepared by the authors.

The results suggest that ineffective formation is related to a lack of coordination between residency program participants, the absence of clear governance strategies, and deficiencies in pedagogical planning. To overcome these obstacles, it is essential that clinical management be more integrated into the educational process, aligning itself with the needs of residents and the goal of training professionals to work in an interprofessional and collaborative manner.

- Moment 4: Hypotheses for Solutions

In the fourth stage of the Maguerez Arc, entitled Hypotheses for Solutions, the 5W2H management tool was applied, which aims to structure the implementation of solutions through the clear definition of actions, responsibilities, deadlines, methods of execution, and necessary resources. The approach follows the principle of collaborative strategic planning, in which all those involved actively participate in the process. This principle is aligned with the idea that organizational education should be an integrated, bottom-up and top-down process, covering all areas of work (Padilha et al., 2018). In the context of MHR, this active participation is essential to create a collaborative and integrated learning environment. The representative contribution of all actors was fundamental to the construction of a real and applicable plan, rather than just a theoretical step.

With the definition of the structural problem and its causes, and an understanding of the resident formation process, the group applied the 5W2H tool to identify solutions. The objective was to establish a clear action plan, detailing the necessary actions, those responsible, deadlines, methods of execution, and the resources needed to implement the changes.

During the exercise, the causes of the structural problem were divided into two groups: Group 1 (students) and Group 2 (tutors and preceptors). Group 1 highlighted problems such as deficiencies in the resident evaluation process, lack of standardization in evaluation documents and instruments, lack of clarity about the profile of managers to be trained by the program, and lack of dissemination of the teaching plan. It also indicated the absence of strategic roles and the lack of exclusive working hours for tutors and preceptors, compromising the management and formation of residents. Group 2, in turn, identified flaws such as lack of management support, difficulties in defining the competency profile for residents, and lack of training for tutors and preceptors. It also mentioned the lack of efficient communication between those involved, the lack of restructuring of the pedagogical project, and the need for training for program coordination. Both perspectives revealed flaws that directly impact the quality of the residency, affecting both student learning and management effectiveness.

Table 2 below presents the causes of the structural problem and the proposed actions in a collaborative and integrated manner, considering the perceptions of both

groups. The actions formulated are intended to be implemented jointly, taking into account the needs and challenges raised by all those involved.

Current literature highlights that, for solutions to be effective in contexts such as MHRs, it is essential that health professionals work collaboratively, considering the interprofessional dimensions of their learning (Nunes; Mângia; Lima, 2020). This is in line with the purpose of the residency, which aims to promote a more integrated and collaborative formation, allowing residents to develop skills to solve everyday health problems (Rodrigues; Witt, 2022).

Table 2 - Causes of the structural problem and integrated actions - 5W2H Action Plan.

IDENTIFIED CAUSES	5W2H INTEGRATED ACTION PLAN
1. Deficiencies in the resident evaluation process: inconsistent evaluation, lack of standardized instruments with clear criteria, which hinders objective and continuous evaluation, prevents uniform monitoring of residents, and hinders the management of teaching practices.	What: Review and reformulate the evaluation process to ensure clarity and consistency of information.
	Why: Ensure that the evaluation process is fair, transparent, and appropriate to the training needs of residents.
	When: Immediately, with gradual implementation each cycle.
	Where: In all interactions between tutors, preceptors, and students.
	Who: Program coordination, tutors, preceptors, and students.
	How: Create and apply new assessment tools that consider the profile and skills desired for residents.
	How much: Continuous monitoring and adjustments based on feedback.
2. Shortage of teachers, lack of appointment and workload for tutors and preceptors: lack of appointment and workload, training and clarity in the responsibilities of tutors and preceptors causes disorganization, misalignment and compromises the quality of supervision and learning of residents	What: Define and assign roles, with dedicated working hours.
	Why: Ensure quality in supervision and formation as a whole.
	When: At the beginning of each residency cycle, with annual reviews.
	Where: In all hospital units involved in the residence.
	Who: Program coordination, management, tutors, and preceptors.
	How: Collaborative planning for task assignment.
	How much: Set weekly hours according to needs.
3. Lack of program identity: absence of a clear definition of the profile of the manager to be trained, as well as the competencies and skills they should develop, which creates confusion about the program's objectives and expectations and hinders educational planning and performance evaluation	What: Define the manager profile, with clear competencies and skills.
	Why: Align the goals and expectations of everyone involved.
	When: During the review of the pedagogical project and curriculum.
	Where: In discussions about pedagogical planning.
	Who: Coordination, tutors, preceptors, residents, and managers.
	How: Establish competencies and align with all stakeholders.
	How much: Continuous monitoring of acquired skills.
4. Lack of disclosure of the residency teaching plan: the pedagogical project has not been revised to adjust to the new needs of the residency, and the teaching plan is not adequately disclosed, resulting in a lack of clarity regarding content, methods, teaching practices, and evaluation, which are sometimes obsolete or inadequate	What: Ensure detailed dissemination of the teaching plan.
	Why: Ensure detailed dissemination of the teaching plan.
	When: Beginning of each residency cycle, with periodic reviews.
	Where: Program communication channels.
	Who: Pedagogical coordination, tutors, and preceptors.
	How: Create informational materials and media to detail plans.
	How much: Constant evaluation through student feedback.

5. Immaturity of the process of opening the residency program: new program, lack of strategic planning, absence of clear administrative structures, and lack of necessary management support for the proper and efficient functioning of the program, with failures in communication and coordination	What: Restructure administrative and coordination processes.
	Why: Ensure efficient and effective implementation of the program.
	When: Immediately after identifying faults.
	Where: In the administrative and operational processes of the program.
	Who: Program coordination, hospital management, and tutors.
	How: Implement agile management focused on integration and communication.
	How much: Continuous monitoring and effectiveness indicators.

Source: Prepared by the authors.

From the perspective of clinic management, this moment was particularly relevant, as it allows for the efficient organization and governance of actions and processes that impact the formation and performance of health professionals. It reflects the understanding that organizational education must be dynamic and continuous, articulating the different levels of action within the organization (Mendes, 2019). By adopting this approach, participants ensure that pedagogical and management actions are not only theoretical but also applicable and sustainable in the long term, promoting a teaching environment focused on the needs of residents and the community.

The use of the 5W2H planning tool is a big deal because it helps you see how to put the proposed solutions into action in a way that fits with how healthcare services really work and what healthcare pros deal with every day. Furthermore, it allows us to understand that the effectiveness of solutions depends not only on the organization of tasks, but also on the continuous training of preceptors and tutors, efficient communication between all those involved, and strategic management that integrates the different parts of the program. Therefore, the greatest challenge for clinical management in this context is to ensure that the solutions proposed in the action plan are sustainable and involve the different actors in a continuous process of learning and adaptation. The literature (Oliveira; Cavalcante; Pinto, 2023) indicates that strategic planning in multiprofessional residencies should be flexible and dynamic, capable of responding quickly to changes in health service demands and the formation needs of residents.

- Moment 5: Application of Reality

The fifth stage of the Arco de Magueres application process was Application to Reality, which began with workshops involving a series of discussions and practical actions. At this stage, the connection between the clinic's management model and the Arco de Magueres methodology became evident, as both promote an integrated approach between health management, health care, and health education, with an emphasis on a critical and reflective perspective. The transformation of practices and the promotion of comprehensive care were central points of discussion, directly reflecting the principles of clinic management (Padilha et al., 2018), which aim to transform everyday practices in health services, promoting collaboration among professionals.

The main objective of this moment was to transform the observed reality. In this context, the problematization carried out in the workshops enabled the practical application of the knowledge acquired, bringing the participants closer to everyday hospital life. Upon adopting the MP, the group engaged in five workshops with the active participation of those involved in the problem. This format allowed solutions to be developed collaboratively and aligned with the real needs of the work environment.

Since the collaborative learning process in contexts such as MHRs must be based on practices that integrate diverse professional formations to promote interprofessionality and improve health care (Gomes et al., 2023). In this sense, the role of multiprofessional residencies goes beyond simple technical qualification and should be environments for transforming practices and learning challenges, aligned with the needs of users and the SUS (Flor et al., 2023).

The activities carried out in the workshops, such as the discussion of difficulties observed in working conditions in hospital sectors, provided an opportunity for in-depth reflection on aspects of hospital management in the context of residency programs. The development of strategies to improve management, based on the principles of the SUS and EBSEH, was one of the main points discussed. The growing complexity of professional interactions in hospitals, coupled with the need for balanced governance, required strategic decisions based on the intelligent use of resources and the improvement of management practices, as proposed by clinical management (Schmitz et al., 2021).

Within the scope of multiprofessional residencies, evaluation meetings between coordinators and residents have been an established practice for monitoring the

progress of theoretical and practical learning. These meetings provide a constant space for debate on the disciplines and working conditions in hospital sectors, creating a dynamic environment for the continuous formation of residents. In the context of the research, the importance of equipping residents for health management stands out. The qualification of hospital management in residencies is fundamental for improving care in the SUS, one of the greatest challenges in Brazilian public health (Paiz; Dallegrave, 2017). The workshops enabled the discussion and construction of solutions that aim to optimize the formation of residents, qualifying them for effective management aligned with the needs of the SUS.

The continuous formation of health professionals in multiprofessional residences is closely linked to the improvement of clinical management. Mendes (2019) emphasizes that clinical management principles should be applied in a flexible and innovative way, with the participation of various actors, stimulating their autonomy and ensuring that learning is consistent with the needs of comprehensive health care. The Application to Reality revealed the importance of the issues addressed in the workshops for the transformation of hospital management processes. However, it is essential to reflect on the complexity of the process: improving hospital management does not occur in a linear fashion and requires gradual changes. For example, the standardization of processes, the reformulation and finalization of protocols, the definition of activity schedules, and the standardization of assessment tools are important advances, but they need to be continuously evaluated and adjusted to ensure their effectiveness.

The formation of health professionals in multiprofessional residencies needs to be constantly reviewed, adapting to the demands of health work and the needs of the SUS. The literature indicates that the development of pedagogical strategies that allow critical reflection on work practices and the identification of everyday problems are fundamental to ensuring the quality of learning (Paiz; Dallegrave, 2017). This corroborates the idea that multiprofessional residencies should be a continuous space for the reconstruction of knowledge and transformation of practices, not only in relation to management, but also to health care and education processes (Padilha et al., 2018).

The study contributed to understanding the application of the Maguerez Arc in clinical management in MHR, but also opens up new opportunities for development. The research was conducted in a single university hospital linked to the SUS and EBSERH, which allowed for an in-depth analysis of this specific context, but suggests that the study be expanded to different hospital units. This would allow for the evaluation of contextual variables and the suitability of the methodology to other multiprofessional residency scenarios.

In addition, although representative, the number of participants was limited, which opens up the possibility of expanding the sample in future research to include residents, tutors, preceptors, and coordinators from different types of residency programs and areas of practice, providing a more comprehensive view of the impact of the methodology. Furthermore, although the data collection methodology was diverse and produced important data, it could be complemented by other data sources, such as questionnaires, direct observations, and document analysis, to provide a more robust view of the learning and management processes. These directions for future research represent opportunities to expand understanding of the impact of Arco de Maguerez and improve management formation and practices in MHR.

Final Thoughts

This study demonstrated the strategic potential of the Maguerez Arc methodology for questioning clinical management practices in the context of multiprofessional residency in hospital management. The application of the Arc allowed emerging issues in the daily routine of health services to be addressed in a structured and collaborative manner, promoting practical solutions to challenges involving healthcare, management, and health education.

The clinic's management model, which forms the basis of this study, articulates these three essential pillars of care as an interdependent triad. By applying the Maguerez Arc, it was possible to observe that the integration between these pillars is fundamental for the development of proactive solutions that promote a collaborative learning environment and transformation of practices. The methodology proved to be a catalyst for change by providing a platform for interprofessional dialogue and critical reflection on educational management practices in the hospital.

By involving residents, tutors, preceptors, and coordinators in discussions about daily hospital life, it was possible to identify improvement strategies that favor both the qualification of residents and the improvement of the formation of teachers and managers. These aspects not only contribute to the qualification of professional practice in the SUS, but also establish a solid basis for the formation of efficient hospital management. In addition, they highlight the importance of the Arco de Maguerez methodology in promoting integrated actions among the various actors in the residency program. Teaching, education, and training in the context of multiprofessional residencies can be enhanced by adopting this model, which proposes a more holistic and collaborative approach to hospital management practice.

Interprofessional learning, a central feature of multiprofessional residencies, favors the formation of professionals with technical skills, but also with interactive competencies that are essential for the transformation of health care. Therefore, the study demonstrates that the multiprofessional residency model is, in fact, a challenging and innovative learning space, in which interprofessional practices are essential for building more integrated and humanized care. When applied in a collaborative manner and interconnected with education and care, clinical management has the potential to instigate the transformation of practices and promote the continuous qualification of the professionals involved.

In this sense, the Maguerez Arch has proven to be a tool for solving problems that contribute to building a more dynamic, collaborative teaching environment that is adaptable to the demands of the SUS and health systems. Collaboration between different healthcare professionals, as proposed by the methodology and MHR, will always be a key component in achieving efficient solutions with a real impact on improving healthcare and hospital management.

References

ABBADE, E. B. O impacto da gestão EBSERH na produção dos hospitais universitários do Brasil. **Ciência & Saúde Coletiva**, v.27, n.3, p.999-1013, 2022. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1590/1413-81232022273.44562020>

BARROS, J. C. C.; RESENDE, G. G.; GONÇALVES, R. M.; RORIZ, T. B. A.; ANDRADE, D. D. B. C..
Gestão da clínica: histórico, conceito e prática. **Brazilian Journal of Development**, v.6, n.4,
p.16760-16774, 2020. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.34117/bjdv6n4-008>

BERBEL, N. A. N.; GAMBOA, S. A. S.A metodologia da problematização com o Arco de
Maguerez: uma perspectiva teórica e epistemológica. **Filosofia e Educação**, v. 3, n. 2, p. 264–
287, 2011. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.20396/rfe.v3i2.8635462>

BRASIL. Hospital Universitário Julio Muller. Brasília, DF: HUJM-UFMT, 2022. Disponível em:
<https://www.gov.br/ebserh/pt-br/hospitais-universitarios/regiao-centro-oeste/hujm-ufmt>
Acesso em: 20 mar. 2025.

BRASIL. **Residência Multiprofissional em Saúde: experiência, avanços e desafios**. Brasília:
Ministério da Saúde, 2006.

CARNEIRO, E. M.; TEIXEIRA, L. M. S.; PEDROSA, J. I. S. A Residência Multiprofissional em
Saúde: expectativas de ingressantes e percepções de egressos. **Physis: Revista de Saúde
Coletiva**, v.31, n.3, p.e310314, 2021. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0103-73312021310314>

CASANOVA. I. A.; BATISTA, N. A.; MORENO, L.R. A educação interprofissional e a prática
compartilhada em programas de residência multiprofissional em saúde. **Interface**, v.22, n.sup.1,
p.1325-1337, 2018. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1590/1807-57622017.0186>

FLOR, T. B.M.; MIRANDA, N. M.; SETTE-DE-SOUZA, P. H.; NORO, L. R. A. Análise da formação
em Programas de Residência Multiprofissional em Saúde no Brasil: perspectiva dos egressos.
Ciência & Saúde Coletiva, v. 28, n. 1, p. 281–90, 2023. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1590/1413-81232023281.11292022>

GOMES, D. C.; SEIMA, M. D.; CAPISTRANO, F. C.; SERAFIM, G. M. L. Gestão de programa de
residência multiprofissional em saúde: Dos desafios às estratégias de melhorias . **Temas em
Educação e Saúde**, v.19, n.e023018, p.1-13, 2023. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.26673/tes.v19i00.18650>

MARIN, M. J. S.; LIMA, E. F. G.; PAVIOTTI, A. B.; MATSUYAMA, D. T.; SILVA, L. K. D.; GONZALEZ,
C.; DRUZIAN, S.; ILIAS, M. Aspectos das fortalezas e fragilidades no uso das metodologias
ativas de aprendizagem. **Revista brasileira de educação médica**, v.34, n.1, p.13-20, 2010. DOI:
<https://doi.org/10.1590/S0100-55022010000100003>

MENDES, E. V. **Desafios do SUS**. Brasília: Conass, 2019.

MENDES, E. V. **Os grandes dilemas do SUS**. Salvador: Casa da Qualidade, Tomo I, 2001.

MENDES, E. V. **As redes de atenção à saúde**. Brasília: Organização Pan- -Americana da Saúde,
2011.

MINAYO, M. C. S. (org.). **Pesquisa Social: teoria, método e criatividade**. 18 ed. Petrópolis:
Vozes, 2001.

NUNES, A. S.; MÂNGIA, E. F.; LIMA, H. A. Educação interprofissional em saúde e prática
colaborativa: uma experiência na formação de residentes. **Revista de Terapia Ocupacional da
Universidade de São Paulo**, v.31, n.1-3, p.60-68, 2020. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.11606/issn.2238-6149.v31i1-3p60-68>

OLIVEIRA, A. S. S.; CAVALCANTE, R. D.; PINTO, T. R. Residência multiprofissional nos espaços
da gestão em saúde: limites, possibilidades e desafios para o exercício da preceptoria.
Contribuciones a las ciencias sociales, v.16, n.11, p.28145-28165, 2023. DOI:
<http://dx.doi.org/10.55905/revconv.16n.11-205>

Cenas Educacionais, v.8, n.e22597, 2025.

Doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16761241>

PADILHA, R. Q.; GOMES, R.; LIMA, V.V.; SOEIRO, E.; OLIVEIRA, J. M. SCHIESARI, L. M. C.; SILVA, F. S.; OLIVEIRA, M. S. Princípios para a gestão da clínica: conectando gestão, atenção à saúde e educação na saúde. **Ciência & Saúde Coletiva**, v.23, n.12, p.4249-4257, 2018. DOI: 10.1590/1413-812320182312.32262016

PAIZ, J. C.; DALLEGRAVE, D. Avaliação de um programa de residência multiprofissional como tecnologia educativa para consolidação do quadrilátero da formação em saúde. **Saúde em Redes**, v.3, n.1, p.18-26, 2017. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.18310/2446-4813.2017v3n1p18-26>

PINHEIRO, R; MATTOS, R. Cuidado e Integralidade: Vida, Conhecimento, Saúde e Educação - Apresentação à 3ª edição. In: PINHEIRO, R; MATTOS, R (Orgs.). **Cuidado: as Fronteiras da Integralidade**. Rio de Janeiro: CEPESC/UERJ, ABRASCO, 2008.

RODRIGUES, C. D. S.; WITT, R. R. Mobilização e estruturação de competências para a preceptoria na residência multiprofissional em saúde. **Trabalho, Educação e Saúde**, v.20, p.e00295186, 2022. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1590/1981-7746-ojs295>

SANTOS, T. B. S.; PINTO, I. C. M. Política Nacional de Atenção Hospitalar: con (di) vergências entre normas, Conferências e estratégias do Executivo Federal. **Saúde em debate**, v.41, n.esp.3, p.99-113, 2017. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1590/0103-11042017S308>

SCHMITZ, T. M.; RICHTER, S. A.; CAPELLARI, C.; MARQUES, M. A. R.; GUIMARÃES, M. K. O. R.; KAISER, D. E.; RIBEIRO, M. R. R.; FERREIRA, G. E. Iniciativas de gestão da clínica empreendidas por enfermeiros em posição estratégica de liderança. **Research, Society and Development**, v.10, n.3, p.e17210313149-e17210313149, 2021. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.33448/rsd-v10i3.13149>

SILVA, A. B. B. F.; BORGES, G. S. S.; CORREIA, Y. V. C.; PASSOS, V. A.; CARDOSO, T. M. P. B.; SOUZA, M. C. O cuidar, o olhar subjetivo e a interprofissionalidade: perceptos e trilhas nos processos formativos de residentes em saúde. **Cenas Educacionais**, Caetité-Bahia -Brasil, v.6, n.e18324, p.1-17, 2023. Disponível em: <https://www.revistas.uneb.br/index.php/cenaseducacionais/article/view/18324>

SOUSA, M. A. O.; FALBO-NETO, G. H.; FALBO, A. R. Correlação entre os domínios de competência do tutor e o desempenho estudantil: estudo transversal. **Revista Brasileira de Educação Médica**, v.45, n.3, p.e178, 2021. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1590/1981-5271v45.3-20200214>

VIEIRA, K. R. Uma revisão bibliográfica acerca da gestão de hospitais universitários federais após o advento da EBSEH. **Revista Brasileira de Administração Política**, v.9, n.1, p.157-178, 2016. Disponível em: <https://periodicos.ufba.br/index.php/rebap/article/view/22413>